

Research Paper: Keys to Success in Multinational Companies

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Keys to Success in Multinational Companies

The assignment focuses on Food Products Industry and it provides the reasons behind their success and failure. The companies can only survive in Food Products Industry, if they are able to develop, adopt and adapt such organizational policies which are highly recommended by the leaders of the industry. Organizational policies provide guidelines to all workers on how to manage, improve and excel the quality and performance of all the organizational units, which play an active role in accomplishing the overall organizational mission. The success of the multinational companies serving under food products industry is dependent on their working conditions, organizational behavior and culture. Only those multinational companies are able to maintain and survive in the international food products industries, which are using best practices policy, as this policy helps them in overcoming all those issues which can become hurdles in their performance and success. Best practices policy is a standardized policy for any specific industry, which ensures success and continuous growth for all the companies serving any specific industry worldwide.

Sanitation Policy

One of the most important and basic policies for any food products manufacturing company is sanitation policy. Without effective sanitation or hygiene an organization cannot produce quality and healthy food products; therefore, it is extremely important for an organization to have a well defined sanitation policy for its workforce. Maintenance staff is a group that has to be very well informed about the sanitation policy, as these personnel have to remain mobile in all the units of the organization to ensure cleanliness.

- Effective sanitizing resources and cleaning tools should be given to maintenance staff, so that they would be able to maintain the required level of hygiene in all the organizational units, especially the production unit.
- All the workers should have access to clean water and hand-sanitizers within the toilet facilities to prevent all kinds of diseases. Effective sign boards should be placed within the production units and toilet facilities to encourage proper hand washing practice among the workers.
- Maintenance staff should be given effective trainings related to sanitation procedures and practices and they should be monitored on regular basis to ensure that they are doing their work accordingly (Slocum, Lei & Buller, 2014).

Eating/Drinking Policy

The workers should be strictly informed about the eating/drinking policy, as it also creates a lot of mess and also increases burden of the maintenance staff. The workers should only use the restricted areas for eating/drinking such as cafeteria, or designated tables in the corner of each unit and should leave these areas tidy by disposing all the waste materials such as remaining food, food wraps etc.

Conflict Resolution Policy

Conflict management or resolution policy plays a critical role in an organization, as it helps the staff members in raising their concerns (problems, frustrations, or misunderstandings) and in gaining justice and guidance on how to overcome them in future. Every employee should have the right to raise his/her concerns and he/she should get effective response from the

management over all the concerns raised (Carroll & Buchholtz, 2014). The employees should follow the following procedure in getting their conflicts resolved:

- Discuss the conflict with your immediate supervisor.
- If the conflict is not resolved by the supervisor an employee should submit a written complaint to the head of the department within 5 working days after the meeting held with the supervisor.
- If the employee is still not satisfied with the decision made by the department head, he/she can submit the same complaint to the HR department within 5 working days after the meeting held with the department head. This is the final step and at this level the HR department will call the parties to sit together and resolve the conflict through mutual understanding.

In-house teams Policy

The in-house teams' policy will indicate the employees about any specific happening, event or organizational change. These teams will be designed on the basis of their skills, expertise and competencies, as they would have to deliver the information clearly and accurately within minimum time period. The leaders of the In-house teams will be appointed through elections and they will remain active for one year till the next elections are announced.

Online Team Policy

The online team will be providing 24 hours coverage to the company's stakeholders on phone and internet. This team must be kept aligned with all the business units through intranet facility. All the relevant information would be posted by the members of the team in a

meaningful manner on intranet that will keep the business units updated. The information can be related to order placement that will inform all the relevant departments such as storage, production, sales etc. to fulfill the customer requirements accordingly.

Security Policy

The security policy will help the company in creation of safe work environment for employees and organizational assets. This policy will assist in promotion of human rights, joint venture partnerships, international peace making, and in advancement of best business practices within the industry. The following will be the principles of security policy:

- Regular assessment of security threats to employees and business operations should be made to avoid all kinds of associated risks;
- The employees' locker and cabin keys should be returned to the security in-charge, while departing the office building.
- Appropriate response procedures should be kept in place to minimize the impact of any emergency or security incident, such as earthquake, storms, theft, harassment etc.
- Active programs should be introduced and maintained within the company to develop a strong sense of security responsibility and awareness among all the employees.
- All the security operations should be in accordance with the international and national legal requirements and these should be based on ethical principles.
- The company should ensure that human rights are not violated through its business operations.

- A specialized security team should be formed that would be recording, analyzing and investigating all reported incidents that violated organizational security and the team would have to develop strategies and plans to avoid such incidents at any cost.
- CCTV camera should be placed in all sensitive area to monitor any illegal activity, which could harm the organizational security.

Emergency Evacuation Procedures

The following are the emergency evacuation procedures that all the employees have to follow during drills and in emergency situations such as fire, earthquake etc.

- The employees should evacuate the building immediately after hearing an instruction of emergency control team or an evacuation alarm. They should secure their personal belongings and stop all the activities quickly to avoid any danger.
- Do assist any person, who is in immediate danger, but first make sure if it is safe to do so.
- Follow the directions given by emergency control team and also assist the disabled employees in evacuation of building or factory etc.
- Do not use a lift in a fire to evacuate a building, and make sure to remain away from huge buildings during earthquakes.
- Remain calm and gather in a nominated evacuation assembly area and wait for the instructions from emergency control team before leaving the assembly area.
- Make sure to follow the instructions of emergency control personnel and participate in emergency evacuation drills to remain safe and secure from all life threatening risks.

Key Benefits of Creating Such Policies

Some of the key benefits of having such policies in place are as follows:

- A multinational company cannot maintain and manage its product quality and market presence without any of these policies, as these policies have become a benchmark which have to be fulfilled by the companies to gain customer attention and ultimately market share (Erwin, 2011).
- These policies help an organization in managing ethical business practices, which are compulsory for any organization to achieve success.
- I personally believe that these policies help in bringing transparency in business operations, which can help the employer and management in overcoming all kinds of business risks or threats.

Major Ramifications of not having such Policies

The main ramifications that the company might have faced of not having such policies in place are as follows:

- The company would not be able to effectively run its business operations, as these policies help in removing hurdles or obstacles that occur in any business operation. Such as without sanitation policy a company cannot ensure quality of food products developed as the workforce as well as the maintenance staff would not be taking care of hygiene in all the business units.
- A huge loss of human lives can be faced by a company, if no emergency evacuation procedures are designed by the company, which could be disastrous for the company's image.

- I believe that each of the policy have sound impact on the overall business process of a company; therefore, all these policies must be kept in place and effective changes need to be made within them to manage the growing complexities in the business environment.

Long-term Stability for a Company

The best practices policy can help a company in attaining long-term sustainability in many significant ways, some of them are stated below:

- With the help of security policy a company can save its assets and human capital from all kinds of security risks, which could have become a major problem, if this policy was not established.
- Every business need to fulfill corporate social responsibility and for this the business owners have to make sure that all of its business operations are according to the legal requirements approved during the inception of a business to avoid any legal charges.

These best practices policy helps the business owners in ensuring proper compliance with the national and international business standards, which is considered as a key ingredient for success among the multinational companies.

- I think if an organization wants to maintain prominent image in the minds of its consumers then it should strictly follow the created best practices policy, as it ensures long term stability.

Achieving Competitive Advantage

I believe that my best practices policy will help an organization in attaining competitive advantage over other existing international companies, as each of the practice discussed in this

policy encourages organizational performance and visibility. Companies, which are able to maintain effective presence in the international and national markets, were those companies that were able to inspire the society with their quality business operations and it is must for the companies to effectively implement such practices and policies that help in accomplishing overall business mission (Carroll & Buchholtz, 2014). Nestle Company is using similar best practices policy and it is able to accomplish its business goals at ease.

References

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